

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF THE DAMAGE INITIATION AND THE COMPETITION BETWEEN DIFFERENT MECHANISMS OF $\pm 55^\circ$ FILAMENT-WOUND GLASS-FIBRE/EPOXY-RESIN TUBES

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SUMMARY: The objective of this paper is to investigate the damage initiation mechanisms and the competition between different mechanisms of $\pm 55^\circ$ filament-wound glass-fibre/epoxy-resin tubes under biaxial loading. First, the microstructure, mechanical behaviour and damage initiation mechanisms were determined. Then, micromechanical modelling of the damage initiation was conducted in order to determine the mechanical conditions under which different microcracking mechanisms occur and the critical s_{zz}/s_{qq} ratios which correspond to the change from interfacial failure to microcracking at porosity. The porosity volume fraction should be kept below 5% to avoid any detrimental effect. Failure envelopes of our composite tube were predicted based on the different criteria at meso- and microscopic scales. The predicted results in an internal pressure dominated region are conservative compared with experimental ones. The possible improvement may reside in introducing a variation of the shear modulus due to the matrix viscous effect and the interfacial sliding effect.

KEYWORDS: composite filament-wound tube, interply and intraply porosity, axial tensile, internal pressure and combined loading, damage, transversal cracking, delamination, micromechanical modelling

INTRODUCTION

Filament-wound glass fibre reinforced epoxy (GRE) tubes are increasingly being used for high pressure containment in chemical plant and aerospace applications, and also in the oil and nuclear industry [1-5]. The design of this kind of tube was optimised essentially for the fabrication of internal pressure containers which are frequently thin-walled and possess characterisations like low cost and weight effective utilisation of materials. Their fabrication route consists of impregnating the fibre strands with resin and then winding them on to a rotating mandrel of a predetermined fibre path under controlled tension. The wound part is cured in an oven to form the final product which has continuous fibres of the same orientation and axisymmetrical configuration. The most frequently observed microstructural defects of this kind of composite structure are inter and intra-ply porosity in the matrix, non-uniform fibre distribution (local fibre volume fraction fluctuation and interlayer fibre free resin layer)

and fibre deviation off the $\pm 55^\circ$ alignment. A series of mechanical tests have been carried out with various combinations of hoop and axial stresses. The investigation of mechanisms of failure has shown that there are fibre/interface/matrix interactions and interactions between layers which have a dominant effect on the early stages of mechanical failure and damage (microcracking and delamination) initiation [1-10]. To account for these micromechanical effects, it is necessary to perform analyses of the stress states especially the interply stress components and their sensitivity to the microstructural defects [11].

This paper begins with a description of our numerical models, the material properties and the structure analysed. In the results and discussion section, we will focus on the stress states and their sensitivity to microstructural defects and damage. After a micromechanical analysis, the competition between different mechanisms and the effect of a few important factors will be discussed. Failure envelopes of the composite tube will also be presented.

NUMERICAL MODELLING DESCRIPTION

Material Characteristics of Tubing Structure

The internal and external diameters of the tubes are 60 mm and 65 mm respectively. The average thickness of each ply is 0.417 mm. The lay-up sequence is $[55^\circ/-55^\circ]_3$. The epoxy resin used is CIBA - GEIGY LY 556. The fibres are roving 2400 TEX (Vetrotex). In Table 1 the Young's moduli E and the Poisson's ratios n of the resin and the fibres are shown. The basic constituents of the composite ply (fibres and resin) are assumed as isotropic materials with linear elastic behaviour. Mechanical characteristics of unidirectional ply are needed as input data for the 3D finite element calculations. Many approximate averaging and asymptotic homogenisation techniques have been proposed to obtain the overall characteristics of a heterogeneous material containing periodically or randomly distributed inhomogeneities. In this paper we used the Mori-Tanaka theory [10]. The nominal average fibre volume fraction is 56%. Moreover, each unidirectional reinforced ply is considered as an orthotropic material with two privileged directions: longitudinal (fibre direction) and transversal (perpendicular to the previous) directions. Six independent coefficients are required for its complete mechanical behaviour characterisation. In Table 1 the six homogenised elastic moduli are given expressed in a local orthotropic system (1, 2, 3) as defined in Fig. 1, where E_1 and E_2 are transverse and longitudinal Young's moduli, n_{ij} the Poisson ratios and G_{ij} the shear moduli.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of fibres, resin and a unidirectional ply. Engineering constants

	E (MPa)	n	s_r (MPa)	e_r (%)
Epoxy resin	3400	0.35	40	1.7
Glass fibre	73800	0.23	2400	-

E₁ (Gpa)	E₂ (GPa)	n₁₂	n₂₃	G₁₃ (GPa)	G₂₃ (GPa)
10.26	42.89	0.067	0.28	3.58	4.03

Numerical Models and Results of Numerical Calculation

A whole tube is shown in Fig. 2. The total height of the structure equals $2H = 330$ mm. In the following calculations, it is supposed that the internal pressure $p = 10$ MPa and the tensile force $T=10$ kN imposed on the tube extremity, are uniformly distributed on the corresponding faces. The 3D finite element calculations were first conducted on a long whole tube [11]. The choice of modelling a whole tube was made in order to avoid any hoop boundary condition effect. The stress distribution through the thickness presented in Fig.3 represents typical results for composite shells. The results were obtained for the cases of pure internal $p=10$ MPa ($s_{\theta\theta}=120$ MPa) and pure tensile $T=10$ kN ($s_{zz}=20.37$ MPa), respectively. In the case of pure internal pressure the stress S_{22} which is higher in the internal ply slowly drops by 8% on moving towards the external ply.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Test Procedure and Data Acquisition Systems

Tubular specimens from three different manufacture lots (Lot A, B and C) were tested on a MTS hydraulic tensile machine. Constant crosshead speed of 0.03 mm/s was maintained

Fig. 1. Local orthotropic system

Fig. 2. Geometry features of the numerical models

Fig.3(a,b). Stress distributions for the pure internal pressure (left) and tensile loading (right) expressed in local co-ordinates.

during the pure tensile test. For pure internal pressure and combined loading, the loading rate is 0.16 MPas^{-1} . Several specimens under the same loading conditions were tested. A biaxial testing apparatus and a special gripping system designed by LMARC (Besançon, France), was developed to test the tubular specimens under various loading conditions [6]. This testing facility is capable of applying up to 100 kN axial load in tension or compression, and 80 MPa internal pressure. The reason to choose displacement controlled loading pattern for pure tensile tests is to obtain a well developed delamination process, which should produce same damage mechanisms before the peak force as force controlled loading pattern.

The system recorded axial load and position from the servohydraulic machine; axial and hoop strains from the extensometers; the pressure and piston displacement from the pressure intensifier. Real time data acquisition, storage and test pilotage were achieved by the program Labview. The specimens were also carefully observed during the progress of the test in order to detect the eventual whitening, cracking and delamination which could be then correlated with the load-displacement and AE traces. Some tests were stopped at selected load levels so that further micro-examination could be performed using optical or electron microscopy.

Mechanical Behaviour of Composite Tube Specimens

Pure tensile test results and mechanisms of damage initiation

A typical stress-strain curve up to failure is shown in Fig. 4. There is a pronounced peak at a strain of about 1.2%. The curves are essentially linear and elastic for strains lower than 0.5%. The applied fracture force is 30 kN (corresponding fracture stress 61 MPa) for Lot A tubes and 36 kN (corresponding fracture stress 73 MPa) for Lot B tubes. A significant difference in AE signal intensity was noticed for the three types of tubes. Compared to Lot A tubes, there was a delay (thus moving to higher stress levels) in AE for Lot B and Lot C tubes. The first but very few signals were recorded at 6 MPa for Lot A tubes, at 10 MPa for Lot B tubes and at 24 MPa for Lot C tubes.

Fig. 4. Typical pure tensile stress-strain curve for a Lot B tube.

The first damage mechanism is the matrix cracking, the cracks initiating in the zones free of fibres or in the outer resin skin. The cracks are of mode I nature and often perpendicular to the

macroscopical loading direction. In increasing the stress level, the second damage mechanism is observed and is the transverse cracking. The average value of this stress is about 30 MPa for the tubes tested in this study. Observations of the specimens loaded to a lower stress level showed that the cracks were mainly located at the vicinity of the porosity, indicating the strong effect of porosity on the damage initiation mechanism. Furthermore, these cracks are more numerous in the internal ply where there is more porosity and which is highly stressed. They progress and appear in all plies with increasing stress level. In the case of Lot A and Lot B tubes, localised deformation occurred around one main crack along the filament direction. Delamination then initiates and propagates from the main cracks at the interface between plies, which corresponds to the post-peak plateau on the stress-strain curve in Fig. 4. The cracking was, however, more dispersed in Lot C tubes resulting in some kind of necking as in metals. In this zone, there is no longer adhesion between the fibres and the matrix. The real gauge length of the specimen is much reduced.

Pure internal test results and mechanisms of damage initiation

The pure internal pressure tests were performed at a loading rate of 1.6 bar/s. Pressure was gradually increased to the final values. Typical stress-strain (longitudinal and circumferential) curves for a Lot B tube specimen are shown in Fig. 5. The curves were essentially linear and elastic for strains lower than 1%. The tubes, being much stronger when loaded in this direction, were not tested up to failure in order to examine the damage initiation mechanisms. Lower density of AE was recorded for the three types of tubes in comparison to pure tensile testing.

For Lot B tubes, a few matrix microcracks were observed in the external resin layer at $s_{qq} = 210$ MPa. These cracks did not cause the initiation of transverse cracking. For a higher stress level ($s_{qq} = 320$ MPa), delamination was initiated either due to the intraply matrix cracking or to the interply porosity, being located between the two external plies. Whitening was observed on the outer skin of the tubes though few damage traces were found on a large examination surface. The whitening phenomenon has been investigated by several authors [5] and has been attributed mainly to local interface debonding and matrix cracking. A thorough study is being conducted in order to correlate the local stress state to this phenomenon. A significant difference was noticed between these cracks and the transverse cracks under pure tensile loading. In the case of pure internal pressure, a damaged or microcracked band propagates around the fibres without attacking their interface.

Observation of a Lot A tube specimen loaded to $s_{qq} = 240$ MPa revealed delamination, indicating the possible influence of numerous voids contained in this kind of tube.

Combined loading test results and mechanisms of damage initiation

Tests with various s_{zz}/s_{qq} ratios were also performed at a loading rate of 1.6 bar/s regarding internal pressure. The load was gradually increased to the final values. In general, as far as the mechanical response was considered, the tubes appeared stronger than in pure internal pressure tests. The tubes were not tested up to failure in order to examine the damage initiation mechanisms. The results are presented in two groups regarding the s_{zz}/s_{qq} ratio value.

Tests with s_{zz}/s_{qq} equal to 0.5: A typical stress-strain curve for a Lot A tube specimen is shown in Fig. 6. for s_{zz}/s_{qq} equal to 0.5, i.e. internal pressure testing with an end effect. Very similar

damage initiation mechanisms to axial tensile tests were observed, meaning matrix cracking first ($s_{qq} = 75$ MPa) followed by transverse cracking ($s_{qq} = 110$ MPa). However, the difference between the loading conditions in question and pure internal pressure is that the matrix cracking is more effective in provoking transverse cracking initiation. Transverse cracking was the main damage mechanism which initiated from pre-existing defects, matrix cracking or porosity. For lower stress levels, transverse cracking remained inside one ply. For higher stress levels, however, it crossed several plies. This could be due either to the change of crack direction inside the interply resin layer when the former crosses it, or to just a few cracks having joint traces on the observation plane. It should be noted that there seems to be a correlation between the transverse cracking and the delamination in this kind of loading. A possible process is the transversal cracking giving rise to the delamination at the interface when it propagates through the interply resin layer. For a Lot B tube specimen, delamination was not observed at $s_{qq} = 365$ MPa. Only transverse cracking was initiated at the intraply porosity.

Fig. 5. Typical pure internal pressure stress-strain curves for a Lot B tube.

Tests with s_{zz}/s_{qq} equal to 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3: The purpose of this series of tests was to determine the critical ratio of shift of the main damage mechanism from transverse cracking to delamination. According to the microscopical observations, it seems that the shift occurred for s_{zz}/s_{qq} between 0.2 and 0.3. No transverse cracking was observed for s_{zz}/s_{qq} equal to 0.1 and 0.2. No delamination was observed for s_{zz}/s_{qq} equal to 0.3. A cautionary phenomenon is a heavily damaged band observed at the interface between the two external plies for a test ratio of s_{zz}/s_{qq} equal to 0.1, in which some kind of crazing was produced probably by shear stresses.

Finally, Figure 7a summarises the behaviour of the tubes by relating the damage mechanisms to the applied stresses obtained by microscopical observation and experimental tests.

Fig. 6. Typical stress-strain curve for a Lot A tube tested with $s_{zz}/s_{qq} = 0.5$.

FAILURE PREDICTION OF A PLY BY MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING

Three local failure modes are investigated, which enable to study the competition between different damage mechanisms and to determine the corresponding critical macroscopic loads. The three failure criteria employed here are based on the experimental observations, corresponding to three damage mechanisms: (a) micro-crack initiation from the cavities (porosity), (b) crack initiation at the interface of matrix and fibre by interfacial shear stress, and (c) transverse ply crack initiated at the interface by interfacial normal stress. Using these three local damage criteria, it is possible to determine the corresponding macroscopic applied loads. The method can be explained as following: under a given combined macroscopic loading, the stress fields in each ply can be determined; then both the stresses near the voids, and normal and shear stresses along the interface in each ply can be evaluated by means of micromechanical methods. Subsequently we compare these local stresses with corresponding critical values and determine in this manner the strength of composite tube. The following local values are chosen: $\sigma_{nc} = 80$ MPa, $\tau_c = 53.3$ MPa: when the principle maximum stress near a void reaches 80 MPa, a crack will be initiated at this void; when the interfacial shear stress reaches 53.3 MPa, a crack will be initiated or sliding will take place at the interface; when the interfacial normal stress reaches 80 MPa, a crack will be initiated at the interface by debonding. The choice of 80 MPa for s_{nc} was made after a uniaxial tensile test on pure resin specimens. The maximum value is considered as the fracture strength of the resin. There are no credible values for t_c . Most probably, a ratio smaller than 2 should be used for s_{nc}/t_c , a value of 1.5 was used in this investigation.

Figure 7b shows the predicted results together with the experimental ones. It can be seen that in an internal pressure dominated region the predicted results by micromechanical approach are again conservative. Explanation for such a difference is not evident, since from a mesoscopic point of view, the predicted results have the same tendency (conservative prediction for internal pressure dominated region). It should be mentioned that the

delamination observed in this study is always of interply nature. It is not controlled directly by the stresses inside plies, but depends on the different deformation patterns inside two adjacent plies. The incompatible shear strains between two plies may be the origin of delamination. They change sign when crossing the interface between two plies. The thin resin layer between plies may be the preferred site for delamination initiation.

Fig. 7a. Stress envelope with damage mechanisms and failure modes for different s_{zz}/s_{qq} ratios

DISCUSSION

Comparison with Microscopical Observations

The general tendency predicted by the micromechanical modelling agrees well with micromechanism observation. The threshold stresses increase with an increasing s_{zz}/s_{qq} ratio. In the case of tensile loading, the first damage mechanism was matrix cracking, the cracks initiating at the zones free of fibres or at the outer resin skin. The second damage mechanism observed was transverse cracking, being mainly located at the vicinity of the porosity, indicating the strong effect of porosity on the damage initiation. In the case of internal pressure loading, besides a few matrix microcracks being observed in the external resin layer, for a higher stress level, delamination initiated either from the intraply matrix cracking or from the interply porosity. Whitening was also observed on the outer skin of the tubes though few damage traces were found on a large examination surface.

According to the micromechanical modelling prediction, one should be able to observe, for a tensile test, the cracks initiating at the porosity first for $s_{zz} = 62$ MPa. Some kind of interfacial failure due to interfacial shear stresses should also be visible for a higher stress level. In the case of internal pressure loading, interfacial sliding due to interfacial shear stresses would occur for $s_{qq} = 120$ MPa. The explanation of the absence of this phenomenon in microscopical observations on long tube specimens may reside in the constraint effect of symmetric filament-wound tubes. The sliding along the continuous fibres is or not possible or without any noticeable traces. This sliding might be also partially reversible due to the viscous effect

of the matrix or the elastic nature of it. A special study is under progress at the moment which will help to understand this phenomenon. It can be concluded that this interfacial sliding occurred at a pre-polished free surface at about $s_{qq} = -90$ MPa in compression and $s_{qq} = 140$ MPa in hoop tensile tests. This observation indicates that the choice of $t_c = 53$ MPa for the local interfacial fracture criteria is relatively correct.

On the contrary, for combined loading with $s_{zz}/s_{qq} > 1.9$, another mechanism related to the interface failure, is very detrimental on the composite tube behaviour: debonding by interfacial normal stress. The threshold stress is quite high and increases with the s_{zz}/s_{qq} ratios. The average effect results in very numerous microcracks (one crack for one fibre). A continuous path can be created easily by these cracks which leads to weeping. Stress transfer capacity of the fibres and the tube integrity can be/or not much deteriorated. The macroscopical loading level should be kept below a certain value above which there is still margin before the local stress fields to reach this fracture criterion. A possible way to take into account the effect of both of these two mechanisms is to reduce the corresponding modulus for each of them, namely reducing G_1 for interfacial shear stress damage and E_3 for interfacial normal stress damage.

Fig. 7b. Comparison between micromechanical modelling and experimental results (filled cycle)

Effect of the Choice of Local Criteria

In this study, values of $\sigma_{nc} = 80$ MPa, $\tau_c = 53.3$ MPa were used as the local critical strengths and the absence of coupling of t_c and s_{nc} for the local fracture criteria. Physically, there would be some interaction effect between these two components, as in most cases. However, the experimental data is insufficient to qualify this. Differences in the state of stress and the geometry of the problem will result in vastly different failure mechanisms. The poker-chip strains to failure in the primary loading direction were 0.5-0.8%, so the uniaxial stress state in composite matrices may therefore by itself be a sufficient explanation for low values of transverse composite strains to failure. Furthermore an investigation of pressurised glass-fibre/polyester pipes provides an example of how transverse cracks form early in the

deformation process of a composite structure. Onset of weepage due to transverse cracks occurred at transverse strains of about 0.2% whereas final failure occurred much later. On the other hand, it was recently proposed that with polymers, which have extended covalently bonded structures, molecular disruption in shear is as difficult as it is in tension, and may well be activated by tension instead of shear. Subsequently the failure process in shear tests is almost certainly tension rather than shear.

From a quantitative point of view, the micromechanical prediction gave higher threshold stresses for first damage initiation (transverse cracking) than observations in principally tensile loading regions. Two explanations could be given, one is that the value of s_{nc} was not correctly chosen. The second may be that the stress state effect was not correctly represented by the micromechanical modelling - average theory. To improve this prediction, tests under a similar stress state should be performed in order to determine the critical values for s_{nc} and t_c . Under internal pressure loading, only delamination was observed as a main damage mode at a stress level much higher than that for interfacial shear failure predicted by micromechanical modelling. The plies are subjected to 3D loading with a very large in-plane shear stress, meaning shear along the fibre axis. This situation does not correspond to any known tests in literature.

Effect of the Number and Volume Fraction of Voids (Porosity)

Micromechanical modelling indicates that the average effect of an increase in the void volume fraction on the local stress field, proportionally increased, is small. A local mechanical effect of the porosity is the increase in the stress concentration at the interface. A complementary coefficient of stress concentration K_{tc} should be introduced to take into account this effect, because the micromechanical modelling gives only an average effect. By 2D Finite Element calculation, it was found that for $f_v = 0.05$ and a cubical distribution of fibres and porosity, K_{tc} equals 1.2. This coefficient, larger than one, will still reduce the strength of the interface. The technical importance of this effect is that a void can affect the interface of the fibres in its environment, showing again the detrimental effect in increasing the number of voids.

In practice, a detrimental effect of porosity is to provide more nucleation sites for microcracks and then to reduce the length of the propagation path before their coalescence. To get a quantitative description, the concept of the representative defect is used. The value of $f_v = 0.05$ (volume fraction of porosity) means having one void in the ply thickness direction within a circumferential distance of about 625 mm in the case of ideal distribution. The propagation distance is reduced to 210 mm (half thickness). If f_v increases to 0.1, there may be two voids in the thickness direction (in the worst case), the propagation distance becoming 105 mm. From this point of view, a small size porosity of is more detrimental than a larger size one, for the same volume fraction. The present authors suggest a limit of f_v below 5% in order to avoid any possible detrimental effect.

In this study an aspect ratio of 15 was used for the porosity in the micromechanical modelling. The choice of this value is a result from an average over the microstructural analysis information. According to the microstructural analysis in [1], some of the voids have an aspect ratio larger than 15. The porosity is less stressed with a smaller aspect ratio. This enhancing effect, however, is stabilised for an aspect ratio larger than 14.

CONCLUSIONS

A micromechanical model based on the Mori-Tanaka Theory is used which enables the determination of the local stress fields at the interface and at the porosity in a critically loaded ply of the studied composite tube. The general tendency of the threshold stresses predicted by the micromechanical modelling agrees well with the micromechanism observation. The modelling also provided useful information in order to correlate the microscale damage to the macroscopical behaviour of the tubes under combined loading. The porosity volume fraction should be kept below 5% to avoid any detrimental effect. There still remains some work to be done in order to improve the local criteria and the choice of critical stress values used in them.

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